

THE ROLE OF MOTIVATION IN LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND WAYS TO INCREASE IT AMONG STUDENTS

Khasanova Maftuna Sherali kizi

English teacher at Tashkent state university of Uzbek language and literature
named after Alisher Navai

Abstract. Motivation plays a crucial role in learning foreign languages. There exists an objective need of searching for optimal ways to improve it in the field of education. The information on pragmalinguistics is also taken into account. Evidently, a foreign language is considered to be the main means of intercultural communication. Therefore, the modern methodology focuses on the need to strengthen motivational aspects when learning a language. This article is devoted to the consideration of what motivation is, its types, its role in the process of learning foreign languages, ways and techniques to increase motivation during the lessons, problems associated with the lack of motivation among students.

Keywords: motivation, types of motivation, foreign language, English language, pragmalinguistics, language teaching, cross-cultural communication, communicative competence, demotivation, teaching a foreign language, teaching methods.

Introduction. In the modern world, in conditions of constant intercultural interaction, knowledge of foreign languages is a key aspect of successful communication. Learning English, which is recognized internationally, takes a priority position in solving the issue of communication with representatives of other countries and cultures. The connection between language and thought occupies a central place in theoretical linguistics and philosophy of language. Immersion in another language is not, as research has shown, purely applied in nature and is not limited to communication in this language, but also involves a deep, spiritual process – cognition of the mentality of the inhabitants of the country of the studied language as a set of psychological and behavioral attitudes, traditions, value orientations and mindset.

The methodology. Motivation plays a fundamental role at all stages of learning a foreign language. The very concept of "motivation" (from the Latin *movēre* – "to move") came to linguodidactics from psychology, where "motive" and "motivation" are distinguished, emphasizing the narrower characterization of the former. Motive, along with needs, goals and intentions, constitutes motivation, an external characteristic of the process of carrying out activities. Motivation represents the energetic side and orientation of behavior. It determines a person's choice, gives him strength and perseverance, and makes his behavior appropriate. Learning motivation is a particular type of motivation included in educational activities. The motive in educational motivation is the focus of students on certain aspects of the educational process: for example, to gain knowledge, a good mark, to praise parents or to build desired relationships with peers. Educational motivation is determined by a number of factors: the educational system, the educational institution, the organization of the educational process, the individual characteristics of the student (gender, age, intellectual abilities, self-esteem), the personal characteristics of the teacher and his attitude to teaching, the specifics of the educational subject.

Speaking about the types of motivation, there are external, internal, positive and negative motivations. External motivation is mainly formed by social circumstances, and not by the content of the subject itself. A student may be motivated by the motive of achievement, that is, the desire to achieve success in learning a language, to receive a high mark, diploma, award at a competition, or the motive of self-affirmation, when it is important to earn the approval of other people and achieve a certain status in society by learning a foreign language. The motive of identification is the desire of the student to be like an authoritative person, a hero, an idol. This motive determines, for example, the student's desire to study well in order to understand the lyrics of his favorite foreign band. The affiliation motive encourages learning a foreign language in order to communicate with foreign friends. A student who perceives a foreign language as a means for spiritual enrichment and general development is motivated by self-development. And finally, the prosocial motive comes to the fore when a person learns

a foreign language, because he is aware of the social significance of the teaching. Extrinsic motivation can also be of a narrow personal nature, if mastering a foreign language is perceived as a path to personal well-being. In most cases, external motivation is distant, distant, aimed at achieving the final result of the teaching. However, it should be borne in mind that its stimulating effect on the learning process is often very significant. To maximize the use of such an incentive, it is important to demonstrate to students the progress in language acquisition at each point of study.

External motivation merges with internal motivation and is reinforced by it. Internal motivation is close and relevant to its subject and is determined by the nature of the activity as such. In relation to learning a foreign language, the following variations of internal motivation are divided: communicative (direct communication in the language being studied), linguistic-cognitive (positive attitude to language) and instrumental (positive attitude to various types of work). The communicative type of internal motivation is crucial in mastering a foreign language, since it contains the first and natural need of language learners – communication. The ability to communicate, read and write in a foreign language, and understand foreign speech are basic communication needs.

A foreign language lesson has its own specifics, since the formation of students' communicative competence is put forward as the main goal of learning. The speech warm-up at the beginning of the lesson is already a communicative preface, and speech tasks during the lesson enhance its communicative orientation. The student's acceptance of the task is the starting point for motivation. At the same time, it is important to emphasize the ability of the teacher to formulate the task of the lesson, based on the level of language training of students and their age characteristics. Modern didactics requires a foreign language lesson to have a specific conversational topic with the stated problems and the use of such collective forms of learning as working in pairs, groups, dramatization, role-playing games. Collective forms of work are desirable in the classroom, because they correspond to the very essence of language as a means of communication, assuming the presence of partners.

It is worth noting the difficulties in maintaining motivation of a communicative type in the atmosphere of the native language, when a foreign language acts as a kind of artificial means of communication and the so-called "real situations" are inauthentic. Teaching a foreign language based on communicative tasks introduces students to foreign language culture and participation in the dialogue of cultures, which is currently considered a global goal of mastering a foreign language.

Maintaining students' interest in language as such relates to linguistic awareness of intrinsic motivation. This type of motivation is formed directly through the stimulation of search activity in the language material and the development of linguistic guesswork, as well as indirectly through communicative motivation.

The positive attitude of students towards certain types of work forms instrumental motivation. The main task of the teacher is not to familiarize students with the work on the language material contained in the textbook, but to manage their independent activities. Thus, the teacher designates a specific goal that students should reach in the course of familiarization with the language material, thereby fulfilling the function of a source of information, and promotes the concentration of students' attention on important aspects of the language material, acting as a manager of the process of skill formation and skill development. Instrumental motivation takes into account the temperament of students and gives each of them the opportunity to express themselves in the work that they most like.

There are also positive and negative motivations. The construction "If I learn English, I will get an excellent mark on the exam" marks positive motivation. The construction "If I do not pass the exam, then I will be expelled" is negative. A survey conducted by specialists among students of non-linguistic specialties showed that the majority of respondents when studying a foreign language at a university are driven by a prosocial motive ("it is necessary according to the curriculum", "so as not to be expelled", etc.). The learning process is perceived by such students as forced behavior. A small part of the students pointed to the motive of self-affirmation ("to build a successful career") and the motive of affiliation ("to travel", "to communicate with

foreigners"). Only 5% of students have internal motivation: they study a foreign language because they like it. It can be concluded that students are mainly driven by external motives, while a significant proportion of motivation is negative. This is perceived as a kind of contradiction, since the prestige of foreign language proficiency and its importance in public life have grown, and these circumstances should have formed a positive motivation. However, as we can see, this is not always the case.

Conclusions. Motivation plays a leading role in learning a foreign language. Based on this, the teacher should possess, as far as possible, all available means of its formation and ways to improve it in the conditions of a particular educational institution. Motivation is a side of the student's subjective world, it is determined by his own motives and preferences, conscious needs. The formation of motivation is, first of all, the creation by the teacher of conditions for the manifestation of internal motives for learning, their awareness by the students themselves and further self–development of the motivational and value sphere. Motivation is crucial for activating all psychological processes – thinking, perception, understanding and assimilation of foreign language material. Thus, it is necessary to increase the level of motivation, contributing to the development of intellectual activity among foreign language learners and ultimately striving to increase the effectiveness of the learning process.

The development of educational motivation is a purposeful and long-term process. The systematic application of various methods of increasing educational motivation strengthens the desire of students to acquire knowledge and forms a steady interest in mastering a foreign language.

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